

A TWO-DIMENSIONAL SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY ACTUATOR

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SUMMARY: A theoretical model for the response of a two-dimensional, thermally-driven, shape memory alloy (SMA) actuator is developed. The actuator is assumed to be constructed from a thin layer of SMA bonded to a layer of elastomer. The plate is under a uniformly distributed transverse load. The governing equations is developed by utilizing the classical laminated plate theory, energy balance equations, and a two-dimensional transition model of the SMA layer. A finite element method is employed to solve the nonlinear transient system of equations. Parametric studies are conducted to demonstrate the effects of the elastomer thickness and thermal conductivity, input heating power, and heat sink strength on the overall time response of the SMA actuator.

KEYWORDS: shape memory alloy, elastomer, actuator, two-dimensional, composites, time response, heat sink strength, heating power

INTRODUCTION

The focus of this study is on the time response of a two-dimensional SMA actuator composite plate which is assumed to be constructed from a thin layer of SMA perfectly bonded to a layer of elastomer. In a recent study, the temperature-stress-strain and time responses of a SMA composite beam were investigated by using the energy balance equation for SMA, the equilibrium equations, the constitutive equations, the state equation of phase transition, and a shear-lag stress model [1].

The SMA reinforced composites have been widely studied in recent years. Rogers and baker [2] demonstrated an application of SMA composite in the active structural vibration control of a clamped-clamped graphite/epoxy beam with embedded SMA actuators at the neutral axis. The application of the SMA reinforced composite in structural acoustic radiation control was investigated by Saunders *et al.* [3]. Baz and Tampe [4] have shown that discrete SMA actuator can be used to control buckling of flexible structure. Lagoudas and Tadjbakhsh [5] studied a generalized theory to model the resultant forces and moments for a flexible rod with an embedded line actuator.

Models to simulate the martensitic transformation were developed by Tanaka [6], and Liang and Rogers [7]. Also, a one-dimensional thermo-mechanical constitutive relations for SMAs were developed by Rogers, *et al.* [8]. In order to simulate the thermal-stress behavior of a SMA in a two-dimensional geometry, Ikuta and Shimizu [9] introduced a so called "variable sublayer model."

In this study, a two-dimensional nonlinear transient analysis of a thermally-driven SMA actuator is presented. The classical laminated plate theory is utilized. The energy balance equation for the SMA layer is developed to model the thermal behavior of the SMA layer. The nonlinear constitutive equations of the SMA layer is obtained by combining the plate's constitutive equations with the variable sublayer model for the two-dimensional martensitic transformation. The governing nonlinear system of equations are solved by using a finite element method.

SMA-ELASTOMER ACTUATOR MODELING

Let us consider the actuator shown in Figure 1. The xy coordinate are fixed at the midplane. The plate is composed of two isotropic layers, a SMA layer with thickness, t , and an elastomer layer with thickness, $h - t$. The elastomer layer is perfectly bonded to a heat sink maintained at temperature T_0 . The four edges of the plate are assumed to be simply supported. The plate is subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse load, q .

Initially, the SMA layer is prestrained in the martensitic phase before the transverse load is applied. The stress-strain state in the SMA is indicated schematically as state 1 in Figure 2. Due to the applied load an additional elastic strain is built in the SMA which is indicated as state 2. When heated by passing an electric current above the austenite start temperature, A_s , the SMA transforms into the austenitic phase, attempting to recover the elastic strain and the prestrain. Since the focus in this work is on the time response and the actuation mechanism of the SMA, only small deformation of the plate is considered. Hence, the recover strain is kept within the range of the linear elastic strain (i.e., state 3 indicated in Figure 2). This is the limit for the recovery strain. As a result of strain recovery process, the deflection of the plate is reduced. After the electric current is reduced or removed, the SMA cools down to the martensite phase via conduction through the elastomer to the heat sink. When the SMA reaches the martensite phase, the stress-strain state of the SMA returns to state 2.

By combining the phase transformation, kinematics, strain-displacement, constitutive and equilibrium equations, the following nonlinear system of PDE, in dimensionless form, are developed [10]:

$$A_{44} \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(\theta_x + \frac{\partial W}{\partial X} \right) + A_{55} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \left(\theta_y + \frac{\partial W}{\partial Y} \right) + \Phi = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & D \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + v_e \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right) + D_{33} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial Y} + v_n \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial X} \right) + (D_A + D_{MA} \xi) \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + v_e \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right) + \\ & D_{MA} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial X} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + v_n \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right) + D_{33MA} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial X} \right) + (D_{33A} + D_{33MA} \xi) \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial X} \right) - \\ & A_{44} \left(\theta_x + \frac{\partial W}{\partial X} \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & D \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + v_e \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right) + D_{33} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial Y} + v_n \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial X} \right) + (D_A + D_{MA} \xi) \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + v_e \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right) + \\ & D_{MA} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial X} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + v_n \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right) + D_{33MA} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial X} \right) + (D_{33A} + D_{33MA} \xi) \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial Y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial X} \right) - \\ & A_{55} \left(\theta_y + \frac{\partial W}{\partial Y} \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1c)$$

where the dimensionless, stiffness coefficients D , D_{33} , D_A , D_{MA} , D_{33A} , D_{33MA} , A_{44} , A_{55} , generalized displacements (W , θ_x , θ_y), coordinates (X, Y), and the transverse load Φ are defined in Table 1. ξ is the martensite fraction, and ν_e , ν_n are the Poisson's ratios for the elastomer and SMA, respectively.

Now, let us consider a differential element of the SMA. If the heat loss on the top surface of the SMA is neglected, the energy balance on the SMA becomes

$$C_n \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - Q_n \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} - k_n \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - k_n \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + K_e(T - T_0) = P \quad (2)$$

where $c_n \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$ is the change in the internal energy of the SMA layer with $C_n = \rho_n c$, where ρ_n is the density and c is the specific heat of the SMA. $-Q_n \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t}$ is the energy contributed to the phase transformation of the SMA with $Q_n = \rho_n q_n$, where q_n is the heat of transition of the SMA. $-k_n \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - k_n \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2}$ is the heat conduction in x and y directions through the SMA layer and k_n is the SMA's thermal conductivity. $K_e(T - T_0)$ is the quasi-steady model for the heat conduction lost through the elastomer layer. $K_e = k / [t(h - t)]$, where k is the thermal conductivity of the elastomer. P is the ohmic heating generated by the electric current passed through the SMA layer in the heating process. P is equal to zero if Eq. (2) is used for the cooling process. Equation (2) may be written in dimensionless form as

$$\frac{\partial \Theta}{\partial \tau} - R_{MA} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} - \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial X^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \Theta}{\partial Y^2} + R_k \Theta + S - R_p = 0 \quad (3)$$

where Θ is temperature of the SMA layer, τ is the time, R_{MA} is the heat of transition of the SMA, R_k is the thermal conductivity of the elastomer, S is the heat loss from the SMA layer through the elastomer to the heat sink, and R_p is the ohmic heating.

A linear model for the martensite fraction for the heating and cooling transition processes, respectively, is in the following form [11]

$$\xi = 1 - \frac{T - A_s}{A_f - A_s} + \frac{\sigma}{C_A(A_f - A_s)} \quad (4)$$

$$\xi = 1 - \frac{T - M_f}{M_s - M_f} + \frac{\sigma}{C_M(M_s - M_f)} \quad (5)$$

where C_A and C_M are the material constants which indicate the influence of the stress on the transformation temperatures, A_s and A_f are the start and finish temperature of the phase transformation from martensite to austenite, respectively, M_s and M_f are the start and finish temperature of the phase transformation from austenite to martensite, respectively, and σ is the stress in the SMA which is contributed to the shift of the transformation temperatures. By combining the phase transformation, strain-displacement, constitutive equations with Eqs. (4) and (5), the following relation can be developed:

$$\xi = 1 - \Theta + \frac{(h - t)}{3hC_A(A_f - A_s)(1 - \nu_n)} [(1 - \xi)E_A + E_M \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial Y} \right)] \quad (6)$$

Equations (1), (2) and (6) form a nonlinear system of equations governing the bending of the SMA composite plate subject to both thermal and mechanical loads, where $w, \theta_x, \theta_y, \Theta$ and ξ are independent variables. A finite element model was developed by using the variational method and the following two-dimensional four-node linear element [10]

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^4 \Phi_i W_i \quad \theta_x = \sum_{i=1}^4 \Phi_i \theta_{xi} \quad \theta_y = \sum_{i=1}^4 \Phi_i \theta_{yi} \quad \Theta = \sum_{i=1}^4 \Phi_i \Theta_i \quad \xi = \sum_{i=1}^4 \Phi_i \xi_i \quad (7)$$

where Φ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) are the interpolation functions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The actuator is assumed to be constructed from a layer of 55-Nitinol perfectly bonded to a layer of Dow Corning SYLGARD elastomer. The material properties are listed in Table 3. The boundary conditions of the plate are assumed to be simply supported and thermally insulated on all four edges. A 4×4 mesh of linear rectangular elements is utilized to model the domain. The Crank-Nicolson method is used for the temporal approximation and a time increment of $\Delta\tau = 0.05$ is considered.

To verify the finite element solution, two special cases were compared to closed-form solutions. First, the finite element and closed-form solutions for dimensionless maximum center deflection ($W = wEh^3/qA^4$) of a simply supported isotropic plate ($\nu = 0.3$) were compared, as follows:

Mesh	FEM Results			Closed-Form Solution [12]
	2 x 2	3 x 3	4 x 4	
	0.04337	0.04397	0.04416	0.044341

Next, the stress-free time response for the complete heating and cooling phase transitions of the actuator was compared to the closed-form solution of Ref. [13], as follows ($R_p = 3$, $S = 1.5$ and $R_{MA} = 1.4$):

Heating Time Response		Cooling Time Response	
FEM	CFS Ref. [13]	FEM	CFS Ref. [13]
$\tau = 0.78$	$\tau = 0.78$	$\tau = 0.63$	$\tau = 0.63$

The effects of dimensionless thermal conductivity of the elastomer and the heating power on the overall time response of the actuator are shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, by increasing the heating power the overall time response decreases nonlinearly. Also, one can observe that by enhancing the thermal conductivity of the elastomer the time response is reduced nonlinearly. In addition, it is interesting to note that for any applied heating power there is an optimal value for the thermal conductivity of elastomer beyond which the overall time response of the actuator increases. This optimal value increases as the applied heating power increases. Figure 4 shows the effect of dimensionless thermal conductivity of the elastomer on the overall time response of the actuator for different heat sink strengths. The same

phenomenon, as described for Figure 3, can be seen here. The only difference is that the value of the optimal thermal conductivity reduces by increasing the heat sink strength.

The effects of the thickness of the elastomer layer and the heating power on the overall time response of the actuator are presented in Figure 5. The response time increases nonlinearly by increasing the thickness of the elastomer layer and decreases nonlinearly by increasing the heating power. It is also observed that there is an optimal value for the applied heating power beyond which there is no change on the overall time response. Figure 6 shows the overall time response of the plate as a function the elastomer layer thickness for different heat sink strengths. Again, the response time increases nonlinearly by increasing the thickness and decreases by increasing the heat sink strength. However, beyond a critical value, for the heat sink strength, the time response increases. This means that the actuator's heat loss is faster than the input heat, thus delaying the transformation process.

CONCLUSIONS

A non-linear model for the response of a two-dimensional, thermally-driven SMA-elastomer actuator was developed based on the Classical Laminated Plate Theory, the variable sublayer stress model and a two-dimensional martensitic transformation approximation. A finite element formulation was developed to solve the proposed nonlinear model. The numerical results demonstrated that the input heating power, heat sink strength, the thermal conductivity and the thickness of the elastomer layer play important roles on controlling the time response of the actuator.

REFERENCES

1. Wu, W., Gordaninejad, F. and Wirtz, R. A., "Modeling and Analysis of A Shape Memory Alloy - Elastomer Composite Actuator," *Journal of Intelligent Materials, Systems and Structures*, July, 1996, pp. 441-447.
2. Rogers, C. A. and Baker D., "Experimental Studies of Active Strain Energy Turning of Adaptive Composites," *Proceedings of the 31st Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Long Beach, CA., April 2-4, 1990, pp. 2234-2241.
3. Saunders, W. R., Robershaw, H. H. and Rogers, C. A., 1991, "Structural Acoustic Control of a Shape Memory Alloy Composite Beam," *Journal of Intelligent Materials, System and Structures.*, Vol. 2, pp. 508-527.
4. Baz, A. and Tampe, L., "Active Control of Buckling of Flexible Beam," *Proceedings of the ASME Design Technical Conference*, Montreal, Canada, Vol. 1. DE-16, 1989, pp. 211-218.
5. Lagoudas, D. C. and Tadjbakhsh, I. G., "Deformation of Active Flexible Rods with Embedded Line Actuators," AMD-Vol. 167, *Recent Developments in stability, Vibration, and Control of Structural Systems*, 1993, pp. 89-106.

6. Tanaka, K. and Nagaki, S., "A Thermomechanical Description of Material with Internal Variables in the Process of Phase Transformation," *Ingenieur Archiv*, 51, 1982, pp. 287-299.
7. Liang, C. and Rogers, C. A., "One-Dimensional Thermomechanical Constitutive Relations for Shape Memory Materials," AIAA-90-1027-CP, 1990.
8. Rogers, C. A., Liang, C. and Jia, J., "Behavior of Shape Memory Alloy Reinforced Composite Plates, Part 1: Model Formulation and Control Concepts," *Proceeding of the 30th Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, AIAA-89-1989, 1989.
9. Ikuta, K. and Shimizu, H., "Two Dimensional Mathematical Model of Shape Memory Alloy and Intelligent SMA-CAD", *Proceedings of the 1993 IEEE Micro Electro Mechanical System - MEMS 1993*, Piscataway, NJ, 1993, pp. 87-92.
10. Wu, W., "Modeling and Analysis of One and Two-Dimensional Shape Memory Alloy-Elastomer Actuators," *Ph.D. Dissertation*, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Nevada, Reno, 1996.
11. Lin, M. W. and C. A. Rogers, "Analysis of Stress Distribution in a Shape Memory Alloy Composite Beam," AIAA-91-1164-CP, 1991.
12. Timoshenko, S. and Woinowsky-Krieger, S., *Theory of Plate and Shells*, Mc Graw Hill, 1959.
13. Wirtz, R. A., Gordaninejad, F. and Wu, W., "Free Response of A Thermally Driven Composite Actuator," *Journal of Intelligent Materials, Systems and Structures*, May, 1995, pp. 398-406.

Table 1. Dimensionless Stiffness.

$D = \frac{(h_0^3 - h_1^3)}{3(1 - \nu_e^2)h_0^3}$	$D_{33} = \frac{(h_0^3 - h_1^3)}{3(1 + \nu_e)h_0^3}$
$D_A = \frac{(h_0^3 - h_1^3)E_A}{3(1 - \nu_e^2)h_0^3E_e}$	$D_{MA} = \frac{(h_0^3 - h_1^3)(E_M - E_A)}{3(1 - \nu_e^2)h_0^3E_e}$
$D_{33A} = \frac{(h_1^3 - h_2^3)E_A}{3(1 + \nu_n)h_0^3E_e}$	$D_{33MA} = \frac{(h_1^3 - h_2^3)(E_M - E_A)}{3(1 + \nu_n)h_0^3E_e}$
$A_{44} = \frac{5}{4} \sum_{i=1}^2 G_i \left[h_i - h_{i-1} - \frac{4}{3} (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3) \frac{1}{h^2} \right]$	$A_{55} = \frac{5}{4} \sum_{i=1}^2 G_i \left[h_i - h_{i-1} - \frac{4}{3} (h_i^3 - h_{i-1}^3) \frac{1}{h^2} \right]$

Table 2. Dimensionless Parameters.

Quantity	$M \rightarrow A$ heating	$A \rightarrow M$, Cooling
Time, τ	$k_n t / h^2 C_n$	$k_n t / h^2 C_n$
Temperature, Θ	$(T - M_f) / (A_f - A_s)$	$(T - M_f) / (M_s - M_f)$
Heat of transition, R_{MA}	$q_n / C_n (A_f - A_s)$	$q_n / C_n (M_s - M_f)$
Power ratio, R_p	$Ph^2 / k_n (A_f - A_s)$	
Temperature ratio, S	$(M_f - T_o) / (M_s - M_f)$	$(M_f - T_o) / (M_s - M_f)$
Load, Φ	q / E_e	
Deflection, W	w / h	w / h
Location, X	x / h	x / h
Location, Y	y / h	y / h
Conductivity, R_k	$K_e h^2 / K_n$	$K_e h^2 / K_n$

Table 3. Themophysical Properties of 55-Nitinol and Dow Corning SYLGARD.

Property	Units	55-Nitinol	SYLGARD
Density, ρ	kg/m^3	6500	1050
Specific heat, c	$J / kg, ^\circ C$	883	1422
Thermal conductivity, k	$W / m, ^\circ C$	N/A	0.146
Heat of transition, q_n	J / kg	12600	N/A
Material constant, C_A	$MPa / ^\circ C$	10.3	N/A
Material constant, C_M	$MPa / ^\circ C$	10.3	N/A

Figure 1. Geometry of the laminated SMA-elastomer actuator.

Figure 2. SMA stress-strain relations in austenite and martensite phases.

Figure 3. Effects of input heating power and the thermal conductivity of elastomer layer on the overall time response of the actuator.

Figure 4. Effects of heat sink strength and the thermal conductivity of elastomer layer on the overall time response of the actuator.

Figure 5. Effects of input heating power and the thickness of the elastomer layer on the overall time response of the actuator.

Figure 6. Effects of heat sink strength and the thickness of elastomer layer on the overall time response of the actuator.